

Supplement to Toward Quantitative Electrochemical Nanomachining of III-Nitrides¹

Cheng Zhang, Ge Yuan, Alexander Brunch, Xiaoming Huang, Jie Song, Kanglin Xiong*, Hongxing Tang, and Jung Han

*Email: Kanglin.xiong@yale.edu

1. Modelling the I-V Characteristic of GaN/HNO₃ Electrolyte Interface

The current-voltage (I-V) behavior at the n++ GaN ($N_D = 1 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) /69% HNO₃ electrolyte interface during EC etching is shown in Figure S1. The semi-log plot (red curve) is divided into six regions corresponding to different etching behaviors which are described in detail in the manuscript. In region E (no-etching regime where current is consumed mainly by thermal emission), in the voltage range between -1.0 V and -0.3 V, the I-V curve is fitted by a Schottky diode model working at forward bias as a straight line in semi-log scale (blue curve). When the voltage is above -0.3 V, the current is not yet at the minimum, which is a photovoltaic phenomenon due to the presence of UV photons from fluorescent light. As the voltage goes below -1.0 V, the diode behavior can be complicated by phenomena such as photon-assisted water electrolysis. Thus, for simplicity, only the part of I-V curve between -1.0 V to -0.3 V is fitted and described here.

Figure S1. Current-voltage (I-V) characteristics of the n++ GaN ($N_D = 1 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) /69% HNO₃ electrolyte interface. The applied voltage on GaN is swept from the positive to the negative bias. The black curve shows the I-V behavior in linear scale, and the red curve is the I-V curve plotted in semi-log scale. The semi-log plot is divided into six

¹ Cheng Zhang et al 2018 J. Electrochem. Soc. 165 E513

regions A-F According to different EC etching behaviors. See the manuscript for detailed description of the six regions.

When a negative voltage is applied to GaN relative to the electrolyte, the GaN/69% HNO₃ interface can be treated as a Schottky diode working at a forward bias, whose I-V follows a simple Schottky diode characteristic,

$$I = I_s \left(e^{\frac{qV}{nk_B T}} - 1 \right) \quad (S1)$$

Where I_s , q , V , n , k_B , T are reverse saturation current, elementary charge, bias voltage, ideality factor, Boltzmann constant, and temperature, respectively.

In the voltage range between -1.0 V to -0.3 V, the ideality factor is fitted to be 3.2. The fitted curve is plotted as the blue line in Figure S1, which agrees well with the measurement.

2. Modeling the Time-Resolved Current During Nanoporous Etching

During EC etching at constant biases, the current evolution over time can be modelled by a dynamic electric circuit as illustrated in Figure 2S.

Figure S2. Schematic diagram of an equivalent electric circuit of the etching system, with each component representing a lumped effect. (R_T) ion and transport within nanopore, (D_c) the GaN/electrolyte interface, (R_G) the geometry bottleneck effect and (R_0) other effects including serial resistance and the resistance of the electrolyte.

Considering D_c , R_G and R_0 together as one nonlinear electrical element, the current I across the tip of a nanopore depends on the total applied bias voltage V_0 minus the voltage drop V_1 on R_T . Near the steady-state EC etching condition, the I - V characteristic of the nonlinear element can be approximated by the polynomial function,

$$I = \sigma(V_0 - V_1)^{1/\alpha} \quad (S2)$$

Where σ and α both are fitting parameters, respectively.

The voltage drop V_1 which is due to ion and mass transport R_T can be modeled as a nonlinear resistor,

$$V_1 = \rho L I^\beta \quad (S3)$$

Where ρ is the nonlinear resistance of electrolyte per length, L is the etching depth, and β is a fitting parameter.

The etching rate (porosification rate) is proportional to the current I . Therefore, the etching depth L increases with time as

$$dL = \gamma I dt \quad (S4)$$

Where γ is a linear fitting coefficient.

Combining Equations (S2) - (S4), the differential equation is obtained for the current I as,

$$I^{-\beta-2}(-\beta V_0 - (\alpha - \beta)\sigma^{-\alpha}I^\alpha)dI = \rho\gamma dt \quad (S5)$$

Using Equation (S5), the time-dependent current during EC etching can be modeled and fitted. By using $\alpha = 1$, $\beta = 2.1$, $\gamma = 17 \text{ m}^3/\text{C}$, $\sigma = 1600 \text{ S/m}$, $\rho = 6.25 \times 10^{-4} \text{ } \Omega\cdot\text{m}$, $V_0 = 1.8 \text{ V}$, the etching current is numerically calculated and shown in Figure S3 together with the measured result for EC etching of n++ GaN ($N_D = 1 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) at 1.8 V in 69% HNO_3 .

Figure S3. Modeling of current - time (I-t) characteristics of nanoporous etching of n++ GaN ($N_D = 1 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) at 1.8 V in 69% HNO_3 . The black solid line is the measured I-t curve, and the red dashed line is the fitted line by a dynamic electric circuit model. Inset: measured and simulated I-t curves in log-log scale.

3. Modeling the Time-Resolved Current During Electropolishing Etching

Contrary to the continuous decrease of current and etching speed in nanoporous etching processes, in stabilized undercut electropolishing process, the etching speed remains constant ($\sim 20 \text{ } \mu\text{m}/\text{min}$), and the current first increases and then decreases (black curve in Figure S4 b). The constant etching speed can be interpreted by an electrochemical-reaction-limited process. Herein, a simple etching front length model is proposed to interpret the current - time (I-t) characteristic of lateral electropolishing process. In Figure S4 (a), the etching fronts are labelled as blue rings. As the EC etching proceeds, the etching fronts advance in the radial direction (r direction) at a constant rate ($v = dr/dt$). The total etching front length L is a function of the radius r of the etched regions. L first increases with r and reaches its maximum when the etching fronts meet ($r = a/2$, where a is the distance between two adjacent via hole openings). After that, L begins to decrease with r and finally diminishes. Since the contact area of n++ GaN/electrolyte is determined by L and the n++ GaN thickness (200 nm), the electrical resistance due to ion/mass transport (R_T) is inversely proportional to L . Therefore, at a constant bias voltage, the current I is in proportion with L . Thus, the current I follows the same trend as L when r increases linearly with time. The modeled I-t curve was plotted as red dotted line in Figure S4 (b). The difference between the measured and simulated I-t curves for the first 75 seconds is due to additional vertical etching of n++ GaN before lateral etching starts. On the other hand, the etching rate of GaN (defined as the GaN consumption rate) is proportional to L and the etching speed. Therefore, the GaN etching rate is in proportion with the current I , which also represents the hole generate rate.

Figure S4. Modeling of current - time (I-t) characteristics of in electropolishing process. (a). The model on the dependence of the total etching front length (L) on the radius (r) of the etched regions. Current I is proportional to the total etching front length (L). (b). The I-t characteristics of electropolishing of of n++ GaN ($N_D = 1 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) at 5 V in 69% HNO_3 . The black solid line is the measured I-t curve, and the red dashed line is the modeled line by a linear dependence model of current on the etching front length.

4. Electrical Field Distribution within Nanoporous GaN

The Electrical field distribution in nanoporous GaN during EC etching is simulated by a two-dimensional full-depletion model using the finite element method (FEM). Figure S5 (a) shows the cross-sectional scanning microscope image (SEM) image of nanoporous GaN ($N_D = 5 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) etched at 5 V in 69% HNO_3 . The SEM image is transformed to grayscale and scanned digitally into the simulation software as the input of the nanopores geometry. In the simulation, n++ GaN doping concentration is set as $5 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and the surfaces of the nanopores are assumed to be in ideal Schottky contact with metal with a work function of 4.5 eV. Figure S5 (b) shows the electric potential distribution of the nanoporous GaN with the top and bottom edges biased at 2 V, resulting in a total surface band bending of ~ 2.5 V. Figure S5 (c) shows the free electron distribution in the nanoporous GaN. There are depletion regions around the peripherals of the nanopores, with depleted depths of ~ 7.5 nm from the pore surfaces into the GaN material, and electron concentrations ranging from $1 \times 10^8 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ to $1 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ in these depleted regions. Figure S5 (d) shows the electric field intensity distribution, with a large electric field of up to 13.9 MV/cm in the pore walls. The large electric field intensity is higher than the dielectric strength of GaN (3.3 MV/cm), and will be even higher at the EC etching voltage bias of 5 V. Therefore, the walls of nanopores in Figure S5 (a) are too thin to sustain such a high electric field induced by the voltage bias during EC etching. Thus, the thin walls of nanopores should only be the relic of wider depletion regions which once bear the bias voltage, rather than determined by the high electric field. Furthermore, the electric field intensity in the pore walls herein is in the similar range of the threshold electric field E_{crit} ($3.3 \times E_{\text{GaN}}$) proposed in the dynamic three-dimensional full-depletion model in the manuscript, which describes the dynamic propagation of nanopores driven by highly concentrated electric field at the tips of the nanopores.

Figure S5. (a) Cross sectional SEM image of nanoporous n++ GaN ($N_D = 5 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) etched at 5 V in 69% HNO_3 . (b) Electric potential distribution, (c) Free electron concentration distribution, and (d) electrical field intensity distribution are two-dimensional simulation results using the geometry extracted from the SEM image. In the simulation, the doping concentration of n++ GaN is set as $5 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$; the surfaces of the nanopores are in ideal Schottky contact with metal with a work function of 4.5 eV; the top and bottom edge of the nanoporous GaN material are biased at 2 V, resulting in a total surface bending of $\sim 2.5\text{V}$. In (c), the unit of free electron concentration (n_e) is cm^{-3} .

5. Fourier Analysis of Nanoporous GaN Microscopic Images

To analyze the arrangement and possible periodicities in the nanopores geometry, two-dimensional Fourier transformation (FFT) is conducted on the cross-sectional SEM images of the nanoporous GaN. Figure S6 shows the FFT images of nanoporous GaN ($N_D = 1 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) etched at 1.8 V and 1.4 V in 69% HNO_3 , respectively, as well as the corresponding cross-sectional SEM images. For nanoporous GaN etched at 1.8 V, the FFT spectrum shows mainly the low-frequency region (central bright spot), which suggests a lack of long range ordering. For nanoporous GaN etched at 1.4 V, the FFT image shows parallel lines pattern which is periodic along the y-axis. It indicates that the nanopores are periodic along the x-axis, and weakly correlated along the y-axis.

Figure S6. Cross-sectional SEM image of n++ GaN ($N_D = 1 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) etched in 69% HNO_3 at bias voltage of (a) 1.8 V and (c) 1.4 V and corresponding two-dimensional Fourier transformation images for (b) 1.8 V and 1.4 (d), respectively.

6. Bottleneck Effect on Etching Rate and Morphology

As illustrated in the manuscript, the measurement of I-V curve of GaN/electrolyte interface is carefully conducted by stepping down (rather than ramping up) the voltage bias to avoid the geometry bottleneck issue related with small pores formed at low voltages (Figure S1). A more detailed description of the geometry bottleneck issue is illustrated here.

Geometry bottleneck effect is mainly caused by limitations in mass/ion transport and affects the etching behavior as well as the nanoporous morphology. Figure S7 (a) shows an optical microscopic image of NP-GaN sample by a three-step etching process, i.e., firstly etched at 2.5V for 3 min, followed by etching at 1.5V for 30 min, and finally etched at 2.5V for 3 min again. The etching depth of the last step is almost one order of magnitude narrower than the depth etched in the first step, although the applied bias and the etching time are the same. The distinct difference in the average etch rate of the first and the last step is due to the geometry bottleneck effect imposed by smaller pores morphology formed by etching at 1.5V. Due to the as-formed small pores morphology by 1.5V etching, the subsequent etching at 2.5V become branch- or mesh-like, which is unlike the pore morphology continuously etched at 2.5V for the entire etching process, as shown in Figure S7 (b).

Figure S7. (a) Optical microscope image of NP-GaN regions formed by EC etching at 2.5V for 3mins followed by etching at 1.5 V for 30mins and lastly etching at 2.5V for 3mins. (b) Cross-sectional SEM image of NP-GaN via EC etching at 1.5 V for 60 minutes followed by etching at 2.5 V for 15 minutes. The interface is marked by two blue arrows.